

Effect of Dexamethasone as an Adjuvant to Bupivacaine in Supraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block for Prolongation of Analgesia - A Comparative Study

Abhishek Agrawal¹, Shraddha Agrawal², Lokesh Kumar Nety³, Uttam Roshan Tigga⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, DKS Post Graduate Institute and Research Centre, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India.

²Associate Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, DKS Post Graduate Institute and Research Centre, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India.

³Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, DKS Post Graduate Institute and Research Centre, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India.

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Anaesthesiology and Critical Care, DKS Post Graduate Institute and Research Centre, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India

Received: 05-12-2024 / Revised: 08-12-2024 / Accepted: 10-12-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Uttam Roshan Tigga

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The supraclavicular brachial plexus block is a widely employed regional anesthetic technique for upper limb surgeries, offering effective intraoperative anesthesia and postoperative pain relief. Bupivacaine, a commonly used local anesthetic, provides excellent nerve blockade but its effects are limited to a few hours. To enhance the efficacy and prolong the duration of analgesia, various adjuvants have been studied. Among these, dexamethasone has shown promising results in extending analgesic effects. This study investigates the impact of adding dexamethasone to bupivacaine on the onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks, duration of analgesia, and potential adverse effects.

Materials and Methods: This prospective, double-blind, randomized controlled trial was conducted in a period of February 2024 to November 2024 at DKS Post Graduate Institute and Research Centre, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India, included 80 patients aged 18–60 years, classified as ASA grades I–II, undergoing upper limb surgeries under supraclavicular brachial plexus block. The patients were randomly divided into two groups. Group BD received 28 mL of 0.5% bupivacaine combined with 2 mL dexamethasone (8 mg), while Group BN received 28 mL of 0.5% bupivacaine with 2 mL normal saline. The onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks were assessed using a pinprick test and the Bromage scale, respectively. The duration of analgesia was defined as the time from the onset of the sensory block to the first request for rescue analgesia. Hemodynamic parameters, including heart rate, blood pressure, respiratory rate, and oxygen saturation (SpO₂), were recorded. Adverse effects were monitored for 24 hours postoperatively. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS v17.0, with a significance threshold of $p < 0.05$.

Results: The demographic characteristics of the two groups were comparable. The study revealed significant differences in the onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks between the groups. The mean onset time for the sensory block was slightly prolonged in Group BD (13.18 ± 1.65 min) compared to Group BN (12.53 ± 1.13 min), with a p -value of 0.04. Similarly, the onset of the motor block was significantly longer in Group BD (18.48 ± 2.2 min) than in Group BN (14.75 ± 1.28 min), with a p -value of < 0.001 . The duration of the sensory block was markedly extended in Group BD (667 ± 31.31 min) compared to Group BN (376.75 ± 13.33 min, $p < 0.001$). The motor block duration also showed a significant increase in Group BD (587.13 ± 29.04 min) compared to Group BN (338.5 ± 9.62 min, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, the duration of analgesia was significantly longer in Group BD (720.5 ± 11.86 min) compared to Group BN (430.13 ± 15.55 min, $p < 0.001$). Hemodynamic parameters, including heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, respiratory rate, and oxygen saturation, remained stable in both groups ($p > 0.05$). Notably, no adverse effects were observed in either group throughout the monitoring period.

Conclusion: The study demonstrates that the addition of dexamethasone to bupivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus blocks significantly enhances the duration of sensory and motor blocks as well as postoperative analgesia without associated adverse effects. This finding supports the use of dexamethasone as an effective adjuvant in regional anesthesia for upper limb surgeries. Its incorporation into clinical practice could provide improved pain management and patient satisfaction.

Keywords: Supraclavicular brachial plexus block, dexamethasone, bupivacaine, analgesia, regional anesthesia, sensory block, motor block.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Supraclavicular brachial plexus block (SCBPB) is a widely used and effective regional anesthesia technique for upper limb surgeries. First introduced by Halsted in 1884, it has evolved significantly over the years [1]. The percutaneous approach to the brachial plexus, described by Hirschel in 1911, marked a major advancement, followed by Kulenkampff's classic supraclavicular approach in 1928 [2,3]. SCBPB offers several advantages, such as improved postoperative pain management, reduced use of general anesthesia, and fewer airway-related complications [4,5]. Moreover, it allows for early mobilization, shorter hospital stays, and reduced overall healthcare costs, especially in outpatient settings [6,7].

Local anesthetics like bupivacaine and lidocaine are commonly used in SCBPB. However, their effects are relatively short-lived, lasting approximately 3–4 hours, which limits their efficacy in postoperative pain management [8]. To address this limitation, various adjuvants, including opioids, ketamine, midazolam, and $\alpha 2$ agonists, have been studied for their ability to enhance the duration and quality of nerve blocks. Among these, dexamethasone has emerged as a promising candidate due to its potent anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties [9,10].

Dexamethasone, a glucocorticoid, provides analgesia by reducing inflammation, suppressing nociceptive C-fiber transmission, and decreasing ectopic neural discharge. It also prolongs the effects of local anesthetics by inducing steroid-mediated vasoconstriction, which slows systemic absorption [11]. Recent studies have demonstrated the efficacy of dexamethasone as an adjuvant in prolonging the duration of sensory and motor blocks, as well as postoperative analgesia, when used with local anesthetics in peripheral nerve blocks [12,13].

This study aimed to evaluate the effect of adding dexamethasone as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in SCBPB. Specifically, it sought to compare the onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks, the duration of analgesia, and the incidence of adverse effects between bupivacaine with dexamethasone and bupivacaine with normal saline.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at DKS Post Graduate Institute and Research Centre, Raipur, Chhattisgarh, India and involved patients undergoing upper limb surgeries under supraclavicular brachial plexus block. This time-

bound, double-blind, hospital-based, prospective, randomized, comparative study was carried out between February 2024 and November 2024. Patients included in the study were aged 18–60 years, had an ASA physical status I or II, and were scheduled for surgery under supraclavicular brachial plexus block. Additional inclusion criteria were a BMI between 18.5 and 25 and a weight range of 50–80 kg. Exclusion criteria included patient refusal, bleeding disorders, severe respiratory diseases, neurological deficits involving the brachial plexus, local infections at the injection site, allergies to study drugs, and contraindications such as peptic ulcer disease, diabetes mellitus, hepatic or renal failure, or pregnancy.

The study groups were divided into Group BD and Group BN. Group BD received 28 mL of 0.5% bupivacaine and 2 mL of dexamethasone (8 mg), while Group BN received 28 mL of 0.5% bupivacaine and 2 mL of 0.9% normal saline. Materials utilized included drugs such as 0.5% bupivacaine, dexamethasone, normal saline, and rescue analgesics like injection diclofenac. Equipment included a peripheral nerve stimulator, multi-parameter monitor, general anesthesia setup, and resuscitation tools.

Preoperatively, all patients underwent a thorough evaluation, including routine investigations. Participants were randomized using computer-generated numbers, and informed consent was obtained. Premedication with oral famotidine (20 mg) and alprazolam (0.5 mg) was administered the night before and on the morning of surgery. In the operating room, baseline vitals were recorded, and intravenous access was established. The supraclavicular brachial plexus block was performed under aseptic conditions using a nerve stimulator to confirm the plexus location, followed by the injection of 30 mL of the assigned drug.

Hemodynamic parameters were monitored intraoperatively and for 24 hours postoperatively. Sensory block onset and duration were assessed with a pinprick test, and motor block was evaluated using a modified Bromage scale.

The duration of analgesia was recorded as the time from sensory block onset to the first request for rescue analgesia. The primary objective of the study was to evaluate the duration of analgesia, while secondary objectives included onset and duration of sensory and motor blocks, as well as monitoring for adverse effects such as nausea, vomiting, Horner's syndrome, dyspnea, allergic reactions, and nerve-related complications. Consent

was taken from the patients and ethical clearance was taken from institute for conducting the study

Blinding was ensured by providing prefilled, coded syringes prepared by an anesthesiologist not involved in the study. Both the investigator administering the block and the patients were blinded to group allocation. Adverse events were carefully monitored throughout the study period. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 17.0.

Continuous variables were analyzed with the unpaired t-test, and categorical variables were compared using chi-square or Fisher's exact test. A sample size of 40 patients per group was determined to ensure adequate power for statistical significance, with thresholds set at $p < 0.05$ for significance and $p < 0.01$ for high significance.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Data

Parameter	Group BD	Group BN	p-value
Age (years)	38.4 ± 10.98	40.15 ± 12.32	0.50
Sex (Male/Female)	67.5% / 32.5%	70% / 30%	0.81
ASA Grade (I/II)	75% / 25%	65.79% / 34.21%	0.37
BMI (kg/m ²)	21.82 ± 2.44	22.77 ± 2.49	0.09

Table 2: Block Onset and Duration

Parameter	Group BD	Group BN	p-value
Sensory Block Onset (min)	13.18 ± 1.65	12.53 ± 1.13	0.04
Sensory Block Duration (min)	667 ± 31.31	376.75 ± 13.33	<0.001
Motor Block Onset (min)	18.48 ± 2.2	14.75 ± 1.28	<0.001
Motor Block Duration (min)	587.13 ± 29.04	338.5 ± 9.62	<0.001

Table 3: Duration of Surgery and Analgesia

Parameter	Group BD	Group BN	p-value
Duration of Surgery (min)	116.88 ± 35.71	117.75 ± 31.42	0.91
Duration of Analgesia (min)	720.5 ± 11.86	430.13 ± 15.55	<0.001

Demographic Data

The demographic characteristics of the participants in both groups were comparable. The mean age of participants in Group BD was 38.4 ± 10.98 years, and in Group BN, it was 40.15 ± 12.32 years, with no statistically significant difference ($p = 0.50$). The sex distribution showed a predominance of male patients in both groups (67.5% in Group BD and 70% in Group BN), and the gender difference was statistically insignificant ($p = 0.81$).

Regarding ASA grade, 75% of patients in Group BD and 65.79% in Group BN belonged to ASA Grade I, while 25% in Group BD and 34.21% in Group BN were classified as ASA Grade II, with no significant difference ($p = 0.37$). The mean BMI was slightly lower in Group BD (21.82 ± 2.44 kg/m²) compared to Group BN (22.77 ± 2.49 kg/m²), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.09$) (Table 1).

Block Onset and Duration

The onset time of the sensory block was longer in Group BD (13.18 ± 1.65 min) compared to Group BN (12.53 ± 1.13 min), and this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.04$). However, the duration of the sensory block was significantly prolonged in Group BD (667 ± 31.31 min) compared to Group BN (376.75 ± 13.33 min, $p < 0.001$). Sim-

ilarly, the motor block onset time was longer in Group BD (18.48 ± 2.2 min) compared to Group BN (14.75 ± 1.28 min), with a highly significant difference ($p < 0.001$). The duration of the motor block was also significantly prolonged in Group BD (587.13 ± 29.04 min) compared to Group BN (338.5 ± 9.62 min, $p < 0.001$) (Table 2).

Duration of Surgery and Analgesia

The duration of surgery was comparable between the two groups, with a mean of 116.88 ± 35.71 min in Group BD and 117.75 ± 31.42 min in Group BN ($p = 0.91$). However, the duration of analgesia was significantly prolonged in Group BD (720.5 ± 11.86 min) compared to Group BN (430.13 ± 15.55 min, $p < 0.001$), highlighting the effectiveness of dexamethasone as an adjuvant in prolonging analgesia (Table 3).

Hemodynamic Parameters and Adverse Effects

No significant differences in pulse rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, respiratory rate, or oxygen saturation were observed between the groups throughout the study period ($p > 0.05$). Additionally, no adverse effects such as nausea, vomiting, Horner's syndrome, dyspnea, or allergic reactions were reported in either group. The addition of dexamethasone to bupivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus blocks significantly pro-

longed the duration of sensory and motor blocks and analgesia without compromising hemodynamic stability or causing adverse effects.

Discussion

The present study evaluates the effects of dexamethasone as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus block, specifically focusing on prolongation of analgesia, onset and duration of sensory and motor blockade, and hemodynamic stability. The study found that the addition of dexamethasone resulted in a delayed onset of sensory (13.18 ± 1.65 min vs. 12.53 ± 1.13 min; $p=0.04$) and motor blockade (18.48 ± 2.2 min vs. 14.75 ± 1.28 min; $p<0.001$). These findings align with Gonuguntla et al., who also observed a delayed onset when dexamethasone was used as an adjuvant [12]. This delay could be attributed to dexamethasone's modulation of nerve excitability, though further exploration into this mechanism is warranted.

The addition of dexamethasone significantly prolonged the duration of both sensory (667 ± 31.31 min vs. 376.75 ± 13.33 min; $p<0.001$) and motor blockade (587.13 ± 29.04 min vs. 338.5 ± 9.62 min; $p<0.001$). Similar findings have been reported in studies by Shaikh et al. and Alarasan et al., emphasizing dexamethasone's efficacy in extending the effects of local anesthetics [7,10]. This effect may stem from dexamethasone's anti-inflammatory properties, which reduce nerve inflammation and enhance the quality of nerve blockade.

A notable finding was the significant prolongation of postoperative analgesia in the dexamethasone group (720.5 ± 11.86 min vs. 430.13 ± 15.55 min; $p<0.001$). Pathak et al. and Solanki et al. similarly reported prolonged analgesia durations with dexamethasone as an adjuvant [15,27]. This prolongation is attributed to dexamethasone's inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis and modulation of nociceptive C fibers, enhancing the local anesthetic effect [9,13].

Hemodynamic parameters such as heart rate, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, respiratory rate, and oxygen saturation remained stable across both groups, with no statistically significant differences observed ($p>0.05$). These findings align with Parveen et al., who also reported no significant hemodynamic variations with dexamethasone use [6]. No adverse effects, including nausea, vomiting, Horner's syndrome, dyspnea, or allergic reactions, were noted in either group, supporting the safety of dexamethasone as an adjuvant.

The results demonstrate that dexamethasone is an effective adjuvant for prolonging postoperative analgesia and blockade durations while maintaining hemodynamic stability.

These findings suggest that dexamethasone can reduce the reliance on systemic analgesics, improving patient comfort and enabling early discharge.

Limitations and Future Directions

This study has some limitations:

1. Only ASA I and II patients were included, limiting generalizability.
2. Plasma levels of dexamethasone were not monitored, leaving the mechanism of action (peripheral vs. systemic) unresolved.
3. Follow-up for nerve injury beyond 24 hours was not conducted. Future studies could include ultrasound-guided techniques for precise nerve localization, larger sample sizes, and investigations into other local anesthetics like levobupivacaine and ropivacaine.

Conclusion

Dexamethasone as an adjuvant to bupivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus block significantly prolongs the duration of sensory and motor blockade and postoperative analgesia without adverse effects or hemodynamic instability. Its use is recommended for upper limb surgeries to enhance patient outcomes and reduce postoperative analgesic requirements.

References

1. Islam S, Hossain M, Maruf A. Effect of Addition of Dexamethasone to Local Anaesthetics in Supraclavicular Brachial Plexus Block. *J Armed Forces Med Coll Bangladesh*. 2011; 7(1):11-14.
2. Hirschel G. Anesthesierung des plexus brachialis bei operationen and der oberen extremitat. *Muenchener Medizinische Wochenschrift*. 1911; 58:1555-6.
3. Kulenkampff D. Brachial Plexus Anaesthesia: Its Indications, Technique, and Dangers. *Ann Surg*. 1928; 87(6):883-91.
4. Al-Haddad M, Coventry D. Brachial plexus blockade. *BJA CEPD Reviews*. 2002; 2(2):33-6.
5. Yadav RK, Sah BP, Kumar P, Singh SN. Effectiveness of addition of neostigmine or dexamethasone to local anaesthetic in providing perioperative analgesia for brachial plexus block: A prospective, randomized, double-blinded, controlled study. *Kathmandu Univ Med J (KUMJ)*. 2008; 6(23):302-9.
6. Cummings KC, Napierkowski DE, Parra-Sanchez I, Kurz A, Dalton JE, Brems JJ, Sessler DI. Effect of dexamethasone on the duration of interscalene nerve blocks with ropivacaine or bupivacaine. *Br J Anaesth*. 2011; 107(3):446-53.
7. Kathuria S, Gupta S, Dhawan I. Dexmedetomidine as an adjuvant to ropivacaine in

- supraclavicular brachial plexus block. Saudi J Anaesth. 2015; 9(2):148-54.
8. Movafegh A, Razazian M, Hajimaohamadi F, Meysamie A. Dexamethasone added to lidocaine prolongs axillary brachial plexus blockade. Anesth Analg. 2006; 102(1):263-7.
 9. Ilfeld BM. Continuous peripheral nerve blocks: a review of the published evidence. Anesth Analg. 2011; 113(4):904-25.
 10. Khan F, Singh V. A comparative study of intravenous versus perineural administration of dexmedetomidine in supraclavicular brachial plexus block using 0.75% ropivacaine by ultrasound guided technique in upper limb surgeries. Int J Res Med Sci. 2018; 6(7):2407.
 11. Talukdar M, Begum H, Shoman MM, Khatun UHS. Anaesthetic and analgesic effects of adding dexamethasone to bupivacaine in supraclavicular brachial plexus block—a comparative study. J Bangladesh Coll Physicians Surgeons. 2013; 3:11-7.
 12. Shaikh MR, Majumdar S, Das A, et al. Role of dexamethasone in supraclavicular brachial plexus block. IOSR J Dent Med Sci. 2013; 12(1):01-07.
 13. Alarasan AK, Agrawal J, Choudhary B, et al. Effect of dexamethasone in low volume supraclavicular brachial plexus block: A double-blinded randomized clinical study. J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol. 2016; 32(2):234-9.